

THE DIVERSITY OF BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM THE URINE CULTURES OF OUTPATIENTS AND ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE PROFILES AFTER A MAJOR EARTHQUAKE

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Keywords

Urine culture

Urinary tract infection

Escherichia coli

Enterococci

Klebsiella pneumoniae.

ABSTRACT

*Aim: Urinary tract infections are widely seen throughout the world in any age group, and mostly in females. After a major earthquake in 2023, sanitation problems developed in the region due to several difficulties, environmental pollution as well as behavioural changes in hygiene as people were exposed to survive for a long time period without water and detergent, resulting in several infections. The aim of this study to determine the diversity of bacteria isolated from urinary tract infections of outpatients and the resistance of these bacterial strains against several antibiotics. Method: The study included 796 outpatients who applied at the urology polyclinic of a secondary care hospital between April 2023 and May 2024. It was examined 159 positive urine culture. Findings: The most frequently isolated bacteria from urine cultures were *Escherichia coli* (n:87, 54.71%), coagulase negative staphylococci (CNS) (n:14, 8.80%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (n:12, 7.54%), *Enterobacter* spp. (n:10, 6.28%), and *Enterococcus faecalis* (n:9, 5.66%). Ampicillin and amoxicillin resistance of *E. coli* strains were 48.27% and 42.12% respectively. *E. coli* strains were mostly susceptible against amikacin (98.85%). Conclusion: Natural disasters such as earthquakes and floods may cause environmental pollution, thereby causing an increase in infections. Epidemiological and demographic changes occur in patient groups. Most of these infections can be prevented by taking precautions and environmental recovery.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the urinary tract infections (UTIs) affect approximately 150 million people throughout the world every year and the majority of patients are female. UTIs can occur in both community and hospital settings^{1,2}. The most frequently isolated microorganisms from UTIs are *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Enterobacter* spp., enterococci and staphylococci³.

The American Infectious Diseases Association declared that it is necessary to know the epidemiology of UTIs and antibiotic susceptibility in a region periodically⁴. The resistance rates of microorganisms isolated from UTIs, particularly during prolonged hospital stay and intensive care unit stays, have shown trend of increasing over time⁵. Therefore, European Urology Guidelines have declared that there should not be empirical use above certain rates of antibiotics for which resistance has been detected⁶.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the prevalence of UTIs caused by the change in hygiene behaviours, sanitation problems and several difficulties in the region following the major earthquake in southeast Türkiye February 2023 and to investigate the antibiotic susceptibility of microorganisms isolated from UTIs.

METHODS

A retrospective examination was made of the urine cultures of 796 outpatients who presented to Urology Polyclinic of a major regional secondary care health centre with various complaints between April 2023 and May 2024. The antibiotic susceptibility of isolated bacteria was evaluated.

Volume: 3

Issue: 2

Page: 63– 72

Received: 02.03.2025

Accepted: 07.04.2025

Available online: 30.06.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15835702

Bacteriological tests were performed with standard methods and 5% sheep blood agar, Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar and MacConkey Agar were used for cultivation. The cultures were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. All the urine samples were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 5 minutes, then microscopic examination was performed on the bottom sediment. The patients with pyuria (at least 10 leukocytes/mm³ after the centrifugation of urine) and the samples with 100,000 colony/ml in urine culture were included in the study. Bacteria were identified using conventional methods (colony morphology, Gram staining, catalase test, oxidase test, carbohydrate and citrate utilization, tryptophanase activity, urease production) and the Vitek® 2 Compact automated identification system (bioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France). Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using disk diffusion method according to European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) (Version 12.0, 2022) standards and Vitek® 2 Compact AST cards (bioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France). The strains were evaluated as susceptible (S), intermediately susceptible (I), and resistant (R). Hospitalized patients were excluded the study.

FINDINGS

During the specified period, 314 (39.45%) females and 482 (60.55%) males presented at the urology polyclinic. The urine samples taken from these patients were analysed; 159 (19.97%) showed positive growth, and six hundred and thirteen (77.01%) samples were negative in terms of microbial growth. Contamination was detected in 9 samples of males and 15 samples of females (totally 3.02%) so these were not included in the study. Positive urine culture was determined in 92 (57.86%) females with a mean age of 48.5±30.5 years and in 67 (42.13%) males with a mean age of 67.5±23.5 years.

Of the total 159 bacteria isolated, 126 were gram-negative bacteria (79.24%), and 33 were gram-positive bacteria (20.75%). The most frequently isolated microorganisms were *Escherichia coli* (n:87, 54.71%), coagulase negative staphylococci (CNS) (n:14, 8.80%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (n:12, 7.54%), *Enterobacter* spp. (n:10, 6.28%), and *Enterococcus faecalis* (n:9, 5.66%). The other bacteria isolated from clinical samples were methicillin susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) (n:7, 4.40%), *Acinetobacter baumannii* (n:6, 3.77%) *Pseudomonas* spp. (n:6, 3.77%), *Proteus* spp. (n:4, 2.51%), *Enterococcus faecium* (n:3, 1.88%) and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (n:1, 0.62%) (Table 1).

Table 1. The number and incidence of bacteria isolated from urology patients.

BACTERIA	(n)	(%)
<i>E. coli</i>	87	54.71
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	12	7.54
<i>A.baumannii</i>	6	3.77
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	6	3.77
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	4	2.51
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>	1	0.62
<i>E. faecalis</i>	9	5.66
<i>E. faecium</i>	3	1.88
MSSA	7	4.40
MSCNS	9	5.66
MRCNS	5	3.14

MSSA: Meticillin Susceptible *Staphylococcus aureus*,

MSCNS: Meticillin Susceptible Coagulase Negative Staphylococci, **MRCNS:** Meticillin Resistant Coagulase Negative Staphylococci

Overall, Enterobacteriaceae strains were dominant in both groups. The bacteria most frequently isolated from both female and male patients was *E. coli*. The number of *E. coli* strains was 87 (57 female, 30 male) with a rate of 54.71%. The age range of female patients was ≥18 - ≤82 years, and the male patients were ≥23 - ≤86 years. In the younger and/or older population the incidence of *E. coli* UTIs was found to be similar. These patients were mostly diagnosed with acute and chronic UTIs at the rate of 88.5%. Extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) positivity in *E. coli* strains was determined in 5.74% of female and 3.44% of male patients. Of the total 12 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains, six were isolated from male patients between the ages of ≥61 and ≤81 years, and with one exception, were diagnosed with acute UTI. The remained six strains were isolated from female patients in the age range of ≥36 and ≤87 years, and with one exception, were diagnosed with acute UTI. Only one ESBL positive *K. pneumonia* strain was isolated from a female patient at the rate of 8.33%. The isolation rate of non-fermentative bacteria from both female and male patients was 8.17%. The age distribution of these patients was ≥21 - ≤78.

Thirty three gram-positive bacteria were isolated from patients with urological complaints in the period. The 21 isolates of 33

(63.63%) were identified as Staphylococci and all the others (48.49%) from females. Staphylococcal strains were isolated (36.36%) were Enterococci. These strains were mostly isolated from 21 patients (12.88%), of which 14 isolates were CNS from female/male patients who had been diagnosed with acute (66.66%) and seven were *S. aureus* strains (33.33%). In terms of methicillin resistance, *S. aureus* strains were completely susceptible against methicillin and no methicillin resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) strain was isolated from urinary samples. Of the CNS strains, nine were methicillin susceptible at the rate of 64.28%. The remained five CNS strains (35.72%) were methicillin resistant.

From the total samples, 33 (20.75%) gram-positive bacteria were isolated; 17 from male patients (51.51%) and 16

Table 2. The distribution of bacteria isolated from female and male patients with urological complaints and age range of the patients.

BACTERIA	Female (n; %)	Age/age range of female patients	Male (n;%)	Age/age range of male patients
<i>E. coli</i>	52; 32.70	≥18 - ≤82	27; 16.98	≥23 - ≤86
ESBL (+) <i>E. coli</i>	5; 5.74	≥35 - ≤68	3; 3.44	59, 60, 73
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	5; 41.66	≥39 - ≤87	6; 50	≥61 - ≤82
ESBL (+) <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	1; 8.33	36	-	-
<i>A.baumannii</i>	2; 1.25	21, 78	4; 2.51	≥29 - ≤58
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	2; 1.25	50, 67	4; 2.51	≥34 - ≤66
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	3; 1.88	45, 68	1; 0.63	88
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>	-	-	1; 0.63	37
<i>E. faecalis</i>	2; 1.25	34, 39	7; 4.40	≥40 - ≤91
<i>E. faecium</i>	1; 0.63	37	2; 1.25	59, 70
MSSA	6; 3.77	≥18 - ≤46	1; 0.63	74
MSCNS	4; 2.51	≥20 - ≤55	5; 3.14	≥22 - ≤70
MRCNS	3; 1.88	29, 54, 70	2; 1.25	63, 76

The patients included this study were mostly diagnosed with acute and chronic UTI. It was seen in both male and female patients in every age group. In the female patients, acute cystitis was determined in five patients and chronic pyelonephritis in two patients. In the male patients, acute orchitis (n:2), acute prostatitis (n:2), chronic prostatitis (n:1), and acute urethritis (n:1) were diagnosed. The ages/age ranges of the female and male patients and diagnoses are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Diagnosis and age groups of female and male patients

GENDER	DIAGNOSIS	AGE/AGE RANGE of PATIENTS
Female	Acute UTI	≥18 - ≤87
	Chronic UTI	≥18 - ≤73
	Acute cystitis	≥19 - ≤68
	Chronic pyelonephritis	39, 40
Male	Acute UTI	≥23 - ≤91
	Chronic UTI	≥23 - ≤86
	Acute orchitis	51, 73
	Acute prostatitis	26, 58
	Chronic prostatitis	69
	Acute urethritis	22

The incidences of bacteria causing various UTIs with numbers and rates are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. The incidences of bacteria causing UTIs in female and male patients with numbers and rates.

BACTERIA	DIAGNOSIS	
	Female (n; %)	Male (n; %)
<i>E. coli</i> (n=87)	57; 35.84 Acute UTI (37; 42.52) Chronic UTI (15; 17.24) Acute cystitis (5; 5.74)	30; 18.86 Acute UTI (20; 22.98) Chronic UTI (5; 5.74) Acute orchitis (2; 2.29) Acute prostatitis (2; 2.29) Chronic prostatitis (1; 1.14)
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (n=12)	6; 3.77 Acute UTI (5; 41.66) Chronic pyelonephritis (1; 8.33)	6; 3.77 Acute UTI (5; 41.66) Chronic UTI (1; 8.33)
<i>A.baumannii</i> (n=6)	2; 1.25 Acute UTI (2; 33.33)	4; 2.51 Acute UTI (2; 33.33) Chronic UTI (2; 33.33)
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (n=6)	2; 1.25 Acute UTI (2; 33.33)	4; 2.51 Acute UTI (4; 66.66)
<i>Proteus spp.</i> (n=4)	3; 1.88 Acute UTI (1; 25) Chronic UTI (2; 50)	1; 0.62 Acute UTI (1; 25)
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i> (n=1)	-	1; 0.62 Acute UTI (1; 100)
MSSA (n=7)	6; 3.77 Acute UTI (5; 71.42) Chronic UTI (1; 14.29)	1; 0.62 Acute UTI (1; 14.29)
MSCNS (n=9)	4; 2.51 Acute UTI (3; 33.33) Chronic UTI (1; 11.11)	5; 3.14 Acute UTI (4; 44.44) Acute urethritis (1; 11.11)
MRCNS (n=3)	3; 1.88 Acute UTI (2; 0.40) Acute cystitis (1; 0.20)	2; 1.25 Acute UTI (2; 0.40)
<i>E. faecalis</i> (n=9)	2; 1.25 Acute UTI (2; 22.22)	7; 4.40 Acute UTI (7; 77.77)
<i>E. faecium</i> (n=3)	1; 0.62 Chronic pyelonephritis (1; 33.33)	2; 1.25 Acute UTI (2; 66.66)

The demographic data of patients were collected and gender distribution was analysed. The majority of UTIs are known to occur in female patients, but the sanitation problems and lack of hygiene facilities following the earthquake in February 2023 also affected males in terms of UTIs. An upward trend of male patients could be clearly seen in April and May 2023. Subsequently the numbers of male and female patients were equalized and as expected, the number of female patients increased from the second half of the year until the end of 2023. After that time, the female patient numbers fluctuated but mostly remained above the number of male patients, except in the period of February to May 2024. The increases and decreases in the trends of bacterial UTIs in males and females in the one-year period after the major earthquake are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The gender of patients who presented at the Urology Polyclinic in the one year period after the major earthquake.

The antibiotic susceptibility of bacteria isolated from various UTIs from female and male patients in all age groups was also analysed in this study. *E. coli* strains were mostly resistant to beta lactam antibiotics. Ampicillin resistance was 48.27% and amoxicillin resistance was 47.12% in these strains. Isolated *E. coli* strains were mostly susceptible against carbapenems and aminoglycosides. The most effective antibiotic against *E. coli* strains was amikacin (98.85%). Resistance of *K. pneumonia* strains against ampicillin was 75% observed and these strains were mostly susceptible to cefoperazone-sulbactam (100%) and doripenem (100%). Eight ESBL (+) *E. coli* strains showed high resistance to amoxicillin-clavulanate (100%), ampicillin (100%), nalidixic acid (100%), cefixim (100%), ceftriaxone (100%), ciprofloxacin (100%), and TMP-SMX (100%). One ESBL (+) *K. pneumonia* strain was resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, fosfomycin, gentamycin, levofloxacin, moxifloxacin, nitrofurantoin, nalidixic acid, cefixime, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, and TMP-SMX. Among the non-fermentative bacteria, the antibiotic resistance rates of *A. baumannii* strains against various antibiotic agents were nitrofurantoin 100%, cefixime 100%, ceftriaxone 100%, ampicillin 85.71%, amikacin 71.42%, aztreonam 71.42%, gentamicin 71.42%, fosfomycin 57.14%, and trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole 57.14% were determined. *P. aeruginosa* strains were resistant to nitrofurantoin (83.33%), amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (83.33%). These strains were presented the same resistance rates against fluoroquinolones, quinolones and cephalosporines (66.6% for all). These strains were mostly susceptible to gentamicin (100%) and meropenem (100%). The most effective antibiotic agents against *Proteus* spp. strains were cefoperazone-sulbactam and doripenem with rates

of 100%. These strains were highly resistant to ampicillin (75%), gentamicin (75%), nitrofurantoin (75%), ciprofloxacin (75%), and trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole (75%). As the number of *Proteus* spp. isolates was relatively low, the real resistance rates could not be evaluated as statistically significant. One of the female patients aged 21 years, was found to be pregnant and one carbapenem susceptible *A. baumannii* strain was isolated from urine of this patient. The antibiotic resistance rates of isolated gram-negative bacteria are shown in Table 5.

Gram-positive bacteria isolated from urine cultures were mostly resistant against trimethoprim-sulphomethoxazole and ciprofloxacin at the rates of 66.66% and 51.51%, respectively. Nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin resistance of MSSA strains was 100% and 85.71%, respectively. Ampicillin, levofloxacin and trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole resistance rates were found to be 71.42% for MSSA strains.

In terms of antibiotic susceptibility for MRCNS strains, amoxicillin-clavulanate, ampicillin and fosfomycin resistance were higher than other antibacterial agents at the rate of 80%. MSCNS strains were not resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate and fosfomycin. Both MRCNS and MSCNS strains were completely (100%) susceptible to amikacin.

The most effective antibacterials were beta lactams against *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* strains. These isolates were completely resistant to fosfomycin and trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole (Table 6).

Table 5. The antibiotic resistance rates of gram-negative bacteria isolated from the urine cultures of outpatients

ANTIBIOTICS	<i>E.coli</i> (87) n/N	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (12) n/N	<i>A. baumannii</i> (6) n/N	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (6) n/N	<i>Proteus spp.</i> (4) n/N	<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i> (1) n/N
Amikacin	0	0	5/6 83.33 %	0	¼ 25 %	0
Amoxicillin - Clavulanic acid	41/87 47.12 %	3/12 25 %	6/6 100 %	4/6 66.66 %	2/4 50 %	1/1 100 %
Ampicillin	42/87 48.27 %	-	5/6 83.33 %	2/6 33.33 %	¾ 75 %	1/1 100 %
Aztreonam	11/87 12.64 %	0	5/6 83.33 %	3/6 50 %	¼ 25 %	1/1 100 %
Cefoperazone - sulbactam	3/87 3.44 %	0	2/6 33.33 %	2/6 33.33 %	0	0
Doripenem	2/87 2.29 %	0	3/6 50 %	0	0	0
Fosfomycin	3/87 3.44 %	2/12 16.66 %	4/6 66.66 %	3/6 50 %	0	1/1 100 %
Gentamicin	14/87 16.09 %	3/12 25 %	4/6 66.66 %	-	¾ 75 %	0
Levofloxacin	22/87 25.28 %	6/12 50 %	1/6 16.66 %	4/6 66.66 %	2/4 50 %	0
Meropenem	2/87 2.29 %	0	2/6 33.33 %	0	¼ 25 %	0
Moxifloxacin	17/87 19.54 %	2/12 16.66 %	1/6 16.66 %	2/6 33.33 %	-	0
Nalidixic acid	25/87 28.73 %	5/12 41.66 %	1/6 16.66 %	4/6 66.66 %	-	0
Nitrofurantoin	4/87 4.59 %	6/12 50 %	6/6 100 %	5/6 83.33 %	¾ 75 %	1/1 100 %
Cefixime	34/87 39.08 %	3/12 25 %	6/6 100 %	4/6 66.66 %	2/4 50 %	1/1 100 %
Ceftriaxone	21/87 24.13 %	3/12 25 %	6/6 100 %	4/6 66.66 %	¼ 25 %	1/1 100 %
Ciprofloxacin	27/87 31.03 %	3/12 25 %	1/6 16.66 %	1/6 16.66 %	¾ 75 %	0
Trimethoprim - Sulphamethoxazole	34/87 39.08 %	5/12 41.66 %	4/6 66.66 %	2/6 33.33 %	¾ 75 %	0

Table 6. The antibiotic resistance rates of gram-positive bacteria isolated from the urine cultures of outpatients.

ANTIBIOTICS	MSSA (7) n/N	MRCNS (5) n/N	MSCNS (9) n/N	<i>E. faecalis</i> (9) n/N	<i>E. faecium</i> (3) n/N
Amikacin	0	0	0	-	-
Amoxicillin – Clavulanic acid	0	4/5 80 %	0	1/9 11.11 %	0
Ampicillin	5/7 71.42 %	4/5 80 %	4/9 44.44 %	-	-
Aztreonam	-	-	-	-	-
Cefoperazone - sulbactam	0	0	0	-	-
Doripenem	0	0	0	-	-
Fosfomycin	0	4/5 80 %	0	9/9 100 %	3/3 100 %
Gentamicin	1/7 14.28 %	1/5 20 %	0	-	-
Levofloxacin	5/7 71.42 %	3/4 75 %	0	-	-
Meropenem	0	0 40 %	0	-	-
Moxifloxacin	0	1/4 25 %	1/9 11.11 %	4/9 44.44 %	2/3 66.66 %
Nalidixic acid	7/7 100 %	2/5 40 %	6/9 66.66 %	-	-
Nitrofurantoin	4/7 57.14 %	3/5 60 %	1/9 11.11 %	-	-
Ciprofloxacin	6/7 85.71 %	3/5 60 %	3/9 33.33 %	3/9 33.33 %	2/3 66.66 %
Trimethoprim-Sulphamethoxazole	5/7 71.42 %	2/5 40 %	3/9 33.33 %	9/9 100 %	3/3 100 %

DISCUSSION

UTIs occur in both males and females in every age group, but more often in adults. It is known that sanitation problems and lack of personal hygiene measures can affect the regional epidemiology of UTIs. In consideration of these negative factors, the aim of this study was to investigate the frequency of UTIs, the etiological factors, and antibiotic susceptibility of isolates after the major earthquake in southeast Türkiye in February 2023.

The study sample size was relatively low due to the limited period. A total of 92 (57.86%) female patients and 67 (42.13%) male patients with positive urine culture were evaluated. Compared with the literature, the number of male patients was remarkably high, which was attributed to the

environmental sanitation problems following this major disaster. Avcişik and Altın examined the gender distribution of patients with rates and reported UTI incidence of 83.7% in females and 16.3% in males⁷. In the current study there was seen to be an approximately three-fold increase in male patients with UTIs. Another study reported UTI rates of 70.9% in females and 29.1% in males⁸. In a study by Coşkun and Ayhan UTI incidence was presented to be 66.5% in females and 33.5% in males⁹.

Abdulaziz and Khalid recently reported gram-negative bacteria as an etiological factor in UTIs at the rate of 94%¹⁰. Gülcan et al. showed a frequency of 91.3% for gram-negative bacteria isolated from UTIs¹¹. The current study findings determined gram-negative bacteria isolated from UTIs at the rate of 79.2%.

In various studies worldwide, the most isolated strains from community-acquired UTIs have been reported to be *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* spp. and ESBL positivity in these strains was reported at approximately 25% in Türkiye^{12,13}. However, Kayaaslan et al. Recently showed a higher rate (57.5%) of ESBL in *E. coli* strains isolated from patients with pyelonephritis¹⁴. Özkan et al. reported ESBL positivity in *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* strains at the rates of 42.6% and 13%, respectively¹⁵. In the current study, ESBL existence was 9.19% in *E. coli* strains, and 8.33% in *K. pneumoniae* strains. These rates were relatively low compared to findings in the literature, which was thought to be a result of the limited sample size. The frequency of non-fermentative bacteria isolated from the urine cultures of outpatients in this study was 8.17%. Gajdaçs et al. reported 3.4% incidence of non-fermentative bacteria in a study of outpatients diagnosed with UTI¹⁶. The results of a study by Keskin et al. were similar to those of the current study with a 7.6% rate for non-fermentative bacteria isolated from UTIs of outpatients¹⁷.

An interesting result of the current study was the amount of staphylococci which are rarely seen in males with community-acquired UTI. In a study, gram-positive bacteria isolated from UTIs were reported with a rate of 26% in Türkiye¹⁷. Gram-positive bacteria isolation rate was 20.75% in the current study. Accordingly, the frequently isolated strains were MSCNS and *E. faecalis* and the isolation rates were 27.27% followed by MSSA (21.21%), MRCNS (15.15%) and *E. faecium* (9.1%).

Gram-negative bacteria isolated from urine samples presented the highest resistance against beta lactams while the lowest resistance against carbapenems and aminoglycosides in the current study. In addition, the resistance rates of the first-choice antibiotic agents in UTIs, fosfomycin, nitrofurantoin and trimetoprim-sulphamethoxazole (TPM-SMX), were 12.69%, 20.63%, and 41.26% respectively according to the findings of this study. Bozkır et al. determined 96% nitrofurantoin, 89% piperacillin-tazobactam, 87% amoxicillin-clavulanate, 83% gentamycin, 75% ampicillin, 68% ceftriaxone, and 65% TPM-SMX susceptibility in *E. coli* strains. Moreover, rates of 40% TPM-SMX, 80% ciprofloxacin, and 20% nitrofurantoin resistance were determined in ESBL (+) *Klebsiella* spp in the same study¹⁸. In

the current study, eight ESBL (+) *E. coli* strains were resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate, ampicillin, nalidixic acid, third generation cephalosporines such as cefixim, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, and TMP-SMX and one ESBL (+) *K. pneumoniae* strain was resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ampicillin, fosfomycin, gentamycin, levofloxacin, moxifloxacin, nitrofurantoin, nalidixic acid, cefixime, ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, and TMP-SMX. However, these findings were not statistically significant due to the limited sample size, and can therefore only be a part of epidemiological data or may be evaluated as a reflection of the data of a single centre after a major earthquake disaster.

The antibiotic resistance of non-fermentative bacteria was investigated and *A. baumannii* strains were found to be completely resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate, nitrofurantoin, cefixime, ceftriaxone. *P. aeruginosa* strains were more susceptible than *A. baumannii* strains to the tested antibiotics. The *P. aeruginosa* strains isolated from patients with UTIs were mostly resistant to nitrofurantoin (83.33%), amoxicillin-clavulanate (66.66%), levofloxacin (66.66%), nalidixic acid (66.66%), and ceftriaxone (66.66%). NkontCho et al. also investigated the antibiotic resistance of non-fermentative bacteria and showed 100% resistance against cefepime, imipenem, meropenem, gentamycin, and TMP-SMX¹⁹. In the current study, only one *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* strain was isolated from UTIs and this strain was resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate, ampicillin, aztreonam, fosfomycin, nitrofurantoin, and cefixime.

Gram-positive isolates were mostly resistant to fosfomycin, nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin. When compared with *S. aureus* strains, the CNS isolates were more resistant to the antibiotics tested and the most effective antibiotics against staphylococci were determined to be amikacin and sefoperazone-sulbactam. These strains showed high resistance to nalidixic acid (71.42%) and ampicillin (61.9%). In a study conducted in Bangladesh, Rahman et al. reported the rate of gram-positive bacteria isolated from UTIs to be 28.74% and the findings indicated that these strains were mostly resistant to cefixime (75%), ceftazidime (60%), ciprofloxacin (30% - 48%), and levofloxacin (25% - 35%)²⁰.

CONCLUSION

The evaluation of the profile of outpatients who presented at the Urology Outpatient Clinic between April 2023 and April 2024 in a health centre operating in the region which had just experienced a major earthquake disaster, showed that the number of male patients was higher than the number of female patients in the first two months, which is a situation not seen under normal conditions throughout the country. It is well known that the majority of patients who present at urology outpatient clinics and are diagnosed with UTI, are female. Although this result was not statistically significant due to the relatively small number of the sample in this study, it can be considered that stress factors such as environmental sanitation problems, changes in hygiene habits, psychogenic effects and nutritional disorders caused an increase in the number of male patients. In addition, when the data for January, March and April 2024, on the anniversary of the earthquake, were examined, the number of male patients was again seen to be higher than the number of female patients, which was thought to be due to psychogenic reasons.

In order to select the appropriate antibiotic agent in the empirical treatment of UTIs, regional variations and etiological agents should be determined, and the antibiotic resistance profiles of these pathogens should be regularly monitored. Although the data obtained in cases of emergency may contradict the general picture, it is valuable in terms of perceiving periodic negativities and temporary threats. These changes, which occurred in the first 1.5 years in the earthquake zone, are gradually starting to normalize and are being put in order with the efforts of governorships, municipalities, provincial health directorates and provincial public health directorates. Future studies in this field will be able to answer the question of ‘where we were and where we came to in epidemiological perspective?’ in the post-earthquake period.

Conflict of Interests: The authors declared no conflict of interests in this study.

Ethical Approval: This study was approved by the Non-Invasive Clinical Research Ethics Committee with the decision number of 05/02/2024-01/18.

Financial support: No financial support for this study was received from any source.

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